

FEATURES OF PROMOTING A NEW PRODUCT VIA THE INTERNET

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Abstract. This article discusses the effect of banner advertising and a set of various activities to bring information about the merits of the product to potential consumers.

Keywords: communication, product, assortment, activity, information, Internet, market, consumers.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРОДВИЖЕНИЯ НОВОГО ТОВАРА ЧЕРЕЗ ИНТЕРНЕТ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается эффект баннерной рекламы и комплекс различных мероприятий по доведению информации о достоинствах товара до потенциальных потребителей.

Ключевые слова: общение, товар, ассортимент, деятельность, информация, Интернет, рынок, потребители.

INTRODUCTION

In a market economy, updating the range of products is becoming one of the important areas of marketing activities of enterprises. This is due primarily to high competition in the consumer market, and secondly, to the dynamics of changes in market conditions. The tastes and preferences of consumers under the influence of market supply are changing rapidly.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Under the promotion of goods is understood a set of various activities to bring information about the merits of the product to potential consumers and stimulate their desire to buy it. The concepts of "marketing communications" and "methods of product promotion" are essentially identical, although experts attribute different groups of methods to product promotion and marketing communications. Thus, direct marketing may refer to methods of marketing communications or to methods of organizing retail trade.

However, it should be borne in mind that other elements of the marketing mix also perform the communication function. For example, sometimes the design of a product, its characteristics, packaging and price tell the consumer much more about the product than its advertising. In this regard, the classification of promotion methods, however, like many other classifications, is relative and is used primarily to facilitate the process of learning marketing.

The establishment of effective marketing communications is carried out in the following sequence: the target audience is identified; its desired response is determined, which in most cases involves a purchase; the objectives of the communication campaign are defined; a communication message is being developed; communication channels are selected; the person who makes the message (transfers information) is determined; feedback is established with the target audience; a general promotion budget (communication budget) is being developed; promotion methods are selected and the effectiveness of communication activities is evaluated.

The target audience is a set of potential or existing buyers or consumers who make or influence purchasing decisions. As the target audience can be considered individuals, groups of people, various segments of the public.

RESULTS

To create initial awareness, the communicator can simply repeat the name of the company or product brand in his message, transmitted several times. Further, consumers who have shown interest should be provided with additional knowledge about the company and / or its specific products. The communication campaign is aimed at developing a favorable opinion among consumers about the subject of interest. The next step is for the switcher to develop a sense of preference for the promoted product among consumers by describing its merits. Next, you need to translate the feeling of preference into a conviction about the need to make a purchase. Not everyone who wants to buy something does so immediately. They may delay the purchase for various reasons. To prevent this from happening the communicator should seek to persuade the consumer to take the final step - to make a purchase. This can be achieved through various means: price discounts, product trials, etc.

After determining the desired audience reaction, a communication message is developed. It defines what to send (the content of the call), how to send it (in terms of the logic of the call), its structure, and how to send (in terms of its execution) the format of the message.

The content of a communication message can be based on three principles: rational, emotional and moral. The choice of one of them is determined by the composition of the target audience and the nature of the advertised product.

Banner advertising. The most common type of advertising on the Internet is banner advertising. Banner advertising is rightly considered the most popular way to increase traffic (attract visitors) to a web page, a means of attracting new customers, as well as a powerful tool for image advertising on the Internet.

Typically, a banner is a rectangular GIF or JPG graphic, although there are banners created using JAVA, ShockWave, and so on. Advertising banners are graphic and text. Graphic banners are usually a static or animated image of a certain size (the most common formats are 480*60 and 100*100). Text banners are any text of a certain size containing hyperlinks to the advertised site or to its specific pages. The banner is placed on the web publisher's page and has a hyperlink to the advertiser's server.

A banner is a billboard on the Internet that performs two functions:

serves to advertise and promote the campaign brand, as well as inform about its products - everyone who sees a banner on a particular Internet resource is considered covered by the advertising campaign;

is a means of attracting visitors to the electronic representation (website) of the advertised company. Everyone who came to the advertised site using a banner is considered to be attracted visitors, who later form the target audience of the resource.

There are three main methods of banner advertising:

Banner exchange systems are services that provide the display of their banners on other pages and, in addition, allow you to automate the interchange and display of banners between different sites - participants in the systems. How does this process take place. Having registered in the banner exchange system, you should upload your own banner into it and insert a special code into your pages (which are supposed to display other people's banners). Every time these pages are loaded, banners of other sites are shown on them. Each banner display is recorded on the internal account (account) in the system. But not all impressions of other people's banners are counted. The system retains a commission for the service provided to you. It's about 10 - 20%.

The remaining impressions can be spent at your discretion: either accumulate them (some systems buy out their impressions),

The banner display system provides for the placement of banners within a particular site at the choice of the company that owns that site. Some of the systems allow you to conduct an advertising campaign more flexibly:

- show your banners only on a specific, selected group of servers;

- show banners at a set intensity or only at times you specify;

- do not re-show the banner to a user who has already seen it.

Advertising in banner networks has a number of unique properties: it has a low cost and allows you to reach a wide audience. These qualities make advertising in banner networks indispensable for solving such problems as:

- brand promotion;

- holding special promotions;

- announcement of news;

- urgent informing the general public about the events.

Blogs and social networks have become popular ways to communicate and organize communities on the Internet. The audience of blogs and social networks is characterized by high activity and a clear range of interests, which allows you to most accurately address advertising to potential customers.

It is also possible to directly negotiate with the webmaster of another page to place banners for each other. It is advisable to exchange with pages that have a similar theme, but keep in mind that exchanging banners with a competitor's website can often do more harm than good.

And finally, you can pay a banner system, a search engine, a directory, or just a popular site to display your banners on their pages.

You should immediately decide what is required from the impressions of the created banner. Do you just need to increase site traffic or is it supposed to attract the target visitor. From this choice depends on what the banner itself will be. So, if you just need to maximize the response of the banner, then you can make it a little incomprehensible, mysterious. If you need to attract the target visitor, then the banner should be designed accordingly. It should give an accurate idea of what is at stake.

Despite the apparent effectiveness of large-format banners, they have negative sides. So, the larger the banner, the larger its size, the longer the page with such a banner loads. There is a possibility that the banner will not have time to load on the page, and the user will already leave it. especially for flash banners. Of course, a flash banner is a new word in banner building, but their large size (volume) reduces the likelihood of a user viewing the page.

The main indicator in banner advertising is the response or effectiveness of the banner. This number is calculated as a percentage. So if the response is 2%, it means that only 2% of the total number of displayed banners were clicked. Now the average response is considered to be 2%. However, there are certain ways in which you can increase the responses of banners.

- the response of the banner located at the very top is higher than the response of the banner located at the very bottom of the page;

- a banner located one-third below the top of the screen gets 70% more response than a banner located at the very top (according to research by www.webreference.com);

- non-standard size banner (125x125) located in the lower right corner of the first page screen gets 228% more response than the standard banner (468x60) located at the very top (according to research www.webreference.com). Text placed above and below the banner increases its effectiveness.

The role of the banner as a means of image advertising should not be discounted. If the response of the banner is 2%, this does not mean that the remaining 98% was wasted. However, a formally designed banner with a clear textual presentation of the content of the site is also not the right solution - its response is usually extremely low. It is not remembered and does not create a positive image. A truly effective banner should be well executed artistically and technically (poor-quality design immediately indicates the lack of respect of the advertised company), as well as be original, possibly intriguing (to arouse curiosity), but at the same time give an idea of the nature of the advertised server / services and create their positive image.

Creating an animated 125 x 125 JPG banner at the previously selected Internet agency is free, as the organization will work with this agency on an ongoing basis. It is advisable to register in the banner exchange network. Then, when loading the site, the user will be shown banners of other sites. Each display of a banner will be taken into account on an internal account in the system. Impressions can be spent at your own discretion: either accumulate them (some systems buy out their impressions), or spend them on showing your banners on other sites. However, in addition to free banner exchange, you should also use paid banner displays on popular Internet sites.

DISCUSSION

As practice shows, the real effectiveness of banner advertising depends not only on the number of possible visitors to the site, but also on determining the possible income from this type of advertising (we can say that this is a common truth), such as:

indirect sales (attracting customers through the company's website);

promotion of goods (advertising of goods, trademark, person);

PR-companies (strengthening and popularization of the image, advertising);

organization of technical support and after-sales service;

improvement of business processes (cost reduction, supply chain optimization, optimization of work with suppliers).

CONCLUSIONS

The approximate effect of banner advertising can be calculated as follows. The effectiveness of a banner is quantified by the click-through rate, which is equal to the ratio of the number of clicks on the banner ("clicks") to the number of banner impressions. The higher the click-through rate, the higher the effectiveness of the advertising campaign is estimated. According to statistics, the average click-through rate is 2%, that is, only two out of a hundred people click on it when they show a banner. In addition, only one person out of four users makes a purchase when clicking on the banner, therefore, if the banner is shown four hundred times, only two people will make a purchase. This means that the coefficient of attracting buyers by placing a banner is: $2/400 * 100 = 0.5\%$.

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